

Principals' Human and Financial Resource Management Skills and Sustainable Education Delivery in Secondary Schools in Delta State

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Abstract

Effective resource management is crucial for sustainable education delivery in secondary schools. This study investigated principals' human and financial resource management skills and their impact on sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State. The research adopted a correlational design. Two research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide this study. The population consisted of 489 principals from public secondary schools in Delta State. A sample size of 120 principals representing 25% was drawn using the Taro Yamane formula. Data were collected using a validated instrument titled principals' human and financial resource management skills Questionnaire (PHFRMSQ) with a reliability coefficient of 0.92 computed using Cronbach alpha method. Simple regression analysis was employed to answer the research questions, and the t-test corresponding to the simple regression was utilized to evaluate the null hypotheses. Findings revealed that management of human resources has a very high relationship with sustainable education delivery while the management of financial resources has an average relationship with sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State. Recommendations include that principals should make the school environment conducive for learning for both students and teachers and devise means of managing the financial resources made available.

Key words: Principals, Resource Management, Sustainable Education

Introduction

An educational system that is effectively and efficiently functional is compulsory for a sustained economy especially in developing countries such as Nigeria. When the education of a nation is sufficiently sustained, it brings about growth of upcoming employees, grooms the leaders of tomorrow, creates a friendly environment for learning and brings about increase in the academic and intellectual aspect. In developing countries like Nigeria, education is seen as an instrument 'par excellence' for achieving national development (FGN, 2013). Achieving national development with a sustained education delivery is difficult without the input of the school administrator also known as the school principal. The principal is that person at the helms of affair who initiates educational policies and programmes, procures and manages both human and financial resources, inspects and supervises school activities and also keep up with laid down standards for implementation of school programmes (Amadi, 2019 in Osakwe & Moses-promise, 2021).

The principal is in position to manage all resources made available to him which includes the human and financial resources. The school principals are responsible for enforcing progressive and advanced school activities by prioritizing learner achievement and teacher effectiveness. They are also responsible for implementing and ensuring structures that lead teachers to set professional development goals for themselves (Bilge & Aslanargun, 2017). The administrative position of the principal in the secondary school is the highest in the hierarchy of authority and he is entrusted with the responsibility of ensuring a sustained education delivery. Human resource management according to Armstrong (2006) in Sunday and Nsobiari (2016) is characterized as a strategic and integrated approach in managing the most essential assets in an organization which are the people that enhances the achievement of the goals of an organization. It therefore means that without the human resource, the organization remains stagnant hence they should be taken care of so as to achieve organizational goals. The management of human resources therefore has to do with the principal combining different management skills geared towards the attainment of a workforce that is skillful and committed so as to achieve organizational goals. Human resource management can be defined as a strategic, integrated and coherent approach to the employment, development and well-being of the people working in organizations (Amie-Ogan, & Epelle, 2021). The human resources within a school consist of the principal, vice principal, teachers, non-teaching staff, and students, all of whom play a crucial role in

the functioning of the school system and share the responsibility of ensuring that the all-round objectives of the school including academics and extracurricular activities are achieved. In other words, it is important to have a cordial relationship between the organization and its employees. The quality of services rendered by an organization is wholly dependent on the quality of human resources available to the organization. Human resource planning is essential for the effective operation and ongoing success of secondary schools, as it is vital for delivering quality education. (Moses & Igwe, 2021).

Akpakwu (2012) asserted that management of human resources involves the ways of recruiting, selection and retention of the people best for the job and grouping them in such a way that their skills and talents will be used. Human resource management also encompasses planning, organizing, directing, acquiring, developing, compensating, integrating, maintaining and separating of human resources in such a way that organizational goals and objectives are actualized (Flippo, 2015). In other words, the principals' human resources management skill is very important and cannot be overemphasized. For the principal to achieve a sustained education delivery through the human resource, he must be able to meet the needs of the employees, make the work environment conducive, relate well with them, create room for staff development, attract and retain high quality manpower, reward success, ensure proper data management, planning and programme implementation that are meant to improve effectiveness that enables the organization function and react to change (Armstrong, 2009 in Sunday & Nsobiari, 2016). The human resource management skills needed by the principal for sustained education delivery in secondary schools are communication skills, leadership skills, problem solving skills, human relation skills and performance appraisal (Osuji & Nweneka, 2022). Other skills includes principals' fairness, decision making, discipline, attitude, use of committee system and so on.

Communication is an indispensable management tool in every organization and the school is not an exemption. It is through communication that workers in the organization socialize by sharing common ideas and feelings among themselves and also learn about the prevalent culture that shapes their behaviour and ideology in the organization (Chukwuka, 2015). Hence the extent to which the principal communicates with his subordinates determines the extent to which goals are achieved. This is so because communication skills of the principal if properly utilized, gives room for exchange of

ideas and opinions, builds up school climate, develops a good listening ability and deals with premature assumptions. Leadership according to Peretomode (2012) is the process of influencing the activities of an organized group towards goal setting and goal achievement. The principal needs this leadership skills to be able to influence the activities of the human resources at his disposal.

Problem solving skills can be defined as the abilities that enable an individual to understand complex situations so as to develop creative and successful solutions. Problem solving skill is also the ability to visualize the organization as a whole. It deals with analytical, creative and initiative skills (Vishwanath, 2012). Principals' human resource skills according to Vishwanath (2012), is the ability to work with, understand and motivate other people as individuals or a group. It requires the principal to be sensitive toward issues and concerns of other people. This human resource skill is also known as the Interpersonal skill that grants the principal the ability to work with people. Every school programme needs routine appraisal because it will enable the principal to ascertain the extent to which the school goals and objectives are achieved. In other words, appraisal of staff is an integral part of the process of ensuring sustainable quality in education (Okeke, 2015). Principals' appraisal skill is an important one because it helps to raise the quality of service rendered by the teachers, helps to maintain standard of performance, locate areas of strength and weakness in programmes and staff; and provide frame of reference for their retention, promotion, transfer and dismissal.

For education delivery to be sustained, financial resources is a necessary ingredient to its success hence the National policy on Education (FGN 2013) posited that quality education is centered on the need for every individual to be equipped with the necessary norms, values, and skills to contribute positively to society. This ensures that education helps individuals understand and participate in the societal and cultural frameworks they are part of. In other words, if investment in education is poor, quality cannot be assured and sustainability becomes difficult. Increased financial investment in education leads to improved quality of education. Many developing countries, including Nigeria, are making significant investments in education, although these efforts are still insufficient. The higher the financial investment made in education the higher the quality of education received. Many developing countries including Nigeria are investing so much in education despite the fact that it is never enough. The financial resources made available to school principals will determine the quality of service that will be rendered if properly managed. It implies that the principal is saddled with the

responsibility of managing the financial resources of the school and this can be achieved if they make budgets, keep records, account for all and sundry and so on. To achieve the objectives of secondary education, the principal must make good use of the financial resources made available to him.

Financial Management skills are referred to as systems that provide a framework for which the resources of an organization are directed towards the attainment of goals of an organization, (United Kingdom, 2014). Effective financial management skills are necessary in fostering transparency, efficiency, accuracy and accountability which enables an organization to achieve its objectives. A school that is well equipped with teaching and learning resources, curriculum dispensation, capacity building programmes and so on is greatly dependent on how the financial resources of the school is being managed. The financial management skills of the principal includes budgeting, accounting, auditing, record keeping and allocation of the schools finances. Therefore the principal should have good management skills so as to be able to control the finances of the school for sustainable education delivery. Davies (2009) in Tichaona, Alfred, Thembinkosi, & Mufunani, (2014) posited that financial control deals with drawing up plans on how the resources of the school can be mobilized, monitored, evaluated and given corrective measures for quality education to be sustained.

A budget is a financial plan that entails a breakdown of all expenses, revenues, with plan for saving, borrowing and spending. Otley and Pollanen (2010) and Brownell (2011) in their studies agreed that it is important for the principal to have idea and skills concerning budgeting so as to be able to evaluate their performance on managing financial resources effectively. The principal with the right budgeting skills will be able to propose and monitor the school budget, and keep checks on both planned financial status and current financial situation. It involves drawing up a projection for the revenue expenditure and identifying positive and negative variances, as well as checking if resources are mobilized effectively. If the principal is able to budget accurately, he will be able to manage the financial resources made available to him and quality education will be delivered. Ihuoma (2010) researched about budgeting for effective control in organizations and found out that budgeting for effective control is a system that uses budget as a means of planning and controlling all aspects of production services and it is a tool for financial control. Keng'ara and Makina (2020) in their study on the effect of budgetary processes and the performance of an organization in relation to non-commercial marine agencies, Kenya revealed that there was a positive significant relationship

between budgetary processes for intense budgetary planning, budgetary control and budgetary implementation, monitoring and evaluation on organization performance. It is against this background that the researchers investigated the relationship between principals' human and financial resource management skills and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Statement of Problem

Quality education is no longer sustained because of lack of adequate resources, poor attitude to work, poor record keeping habit, poor punctuality habits, irregular class attendance, unethical marking of the attendance register and several other unacceptable behaviours which is not in line with the teaching profession and which disrupts the attainment of set goals and objectives. Even in situations where human and financial resources are adequate, quality education is still not sustained due to principals' lack the management skills needed to handle the resources at their disposal. The study therefore investigated the relationship between principals' management of human and financial resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

- 1) How does principals' management of human resources relate to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State?
- 2) How does principals' management of financial resources relate to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the principals' management of human resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between the principals' management of financial resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Methodology

The design for the study was correlational research design. The population consisted of 489 principals from public secondary schools in Delta State and a sample size of 120 principals representing 25% was drawn using the stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using two self-constructed instruments titled principals' human and financial resource management skills Questionnaire (PHFRMSQ) and sustainable education delivery Questionnaire (SSEDQ). The instruments were validated for face content validity by two experts from the department of measurement and evaluation Delta state university, Abraka. The reliability of the instrument was computed using Cronbach alpha method with a reliability index of 0.92. The researchers and one trained research assistant went round to distribute copies of the questionnaire and they were all retrieved on the spot. Research questions were answered using simple regression and research hypotheses were tested using t-test associated with simple regression at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One

How does principals' management of human resources relate to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Simple regression analysis on how principals' management of human resources relate to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard error of the estimate
1	0.960	0.922	0.473	3.94

Table1 showed the correlation value to be 0.92 which means that principals' management of human resources has a very high relationship with delivery of sustainable education in secondary schools across Delta State.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between principals’ management of human resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 2: t-test associated with simple regression analysis on how principals’ management of human resources relates to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	30.863	2.161		12.939	
Human resource management	0.265	0.057	0.358	4.670	0.010

Table 2 showed the probability value to be 0.010 which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence there was a significant relationship between principals’ management of human resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State. In other words, we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Research Question Two

How does principals’ management of financial resources relate to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 3: Simple regression analysis on how principals’ management of financial resources relate to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Standard error of the estimate
1	0.301	0.602	0.315		4.280

Table 3 showed the correlation value to be 0.602 which means that principals’ management of financial resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State has an average relationship with 60%.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between principals’ management of financial resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 4: t-test associated with simple regression analysis on how principals’ management of financial resources relate to sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	50.032	1.789		31.242	
Financial resource management	0.026	0.066	0.031	0.322	0.714

Table 4 showed the probability value to be 0.714 which is higher than the significant level of 0.05. Hence there was a significant relationship between principals’ management of financial resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State. Based on the above, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed that principals’ management of human resources has a very high relationship with sustainable education delivery and there was a significant relationship between principals’ management of human resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State. This finding supports earlier research of Moses and Igwe (2021) who asserted that human resource planning is integral to the efficient running and continued flourishing of secondary schools so as to achieve quality education. In line with this, Armstrong (2009) posited that for the principal to achieve a sustained education delivery through the human resource, he must be able to meet the needs of the employees, make the work environment conducive, relate well with them, create room for staff development, attract and retain high quality manpower, reward success, ensure

proper data management, planning and programme implementation that are meant to improve effectiveness that enables the organization function and react to change.

Findings of the study also revealed that there is an average relationship between principals' management of financial resources and sustainable education delivery in secondary schools in Delta State. This supports the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2004) postulation that for education delivery to be sustained, financial resources is a necessary ingredient to its success hence quality education is centered on the need for every individual to be equipped with the required norm and values of the society. In line with the above, United Kingdom (2014) asserted that financial management skills are systems that provide a framework for which the resources of an organization are directed towards the attainment of goals of an organization,

Conclusion

From the findings, the study has been able to establish the fact that if principals' management of human and financial resource skills are being utilized, there will be sustained education delivery. Hence sound financial management ensure the optimal use of resources, infrastructure development and sustainability of education programs.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were highlighted based on the findings of the study.

1. Principals should make the school environment conducive for learning for both students and teachers and ensure that they make use of their human resource management skills so as to get the best from their subordinates.
2. Principals should also make good use of the financial resources at their disposal and devise means of managing them.

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